

ISic1290

I.Sicily inscription 1290

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 277

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---φ]ίλοι ζητήσον
2. [τεσεμένθ]άδε κεῖμε νήπι
3. [οσώκύμο]ρος Ἐφέσου μεγά
4. [λησδεπολ]είτης · πατρὸς δέ
5. [έστινὸνομ]α Ἀχιλλεύς Στρατο
6. [νίκηδέμ]ου μήτηρ · μοῖρα δ' ἔδω
7. [κέμοιῶ]δε θανεῖν · ἐκκαϊδεκαέκκέδεκα
8. [ἔτηζή]σας κεῖμαι δὲ νῦν
9. [λείπωνφάος] ἠελίοιο · μνημα δέ μοι
10. [άνέθηκε Πόπ]λις Αἴλις Ἀχιλεὺς πατήρ

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Friends seeking me, here I lie, a child who died early, citizen of great Ephesus. The name of my father is Achilleus and of my mother, Stratonike. Fate gave me to die in this place. Having lived for 16 years, I now lie here, having left the light of life. My father, Publius Aeilius Achileus set this up in my memory.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492894

EDCS 39101659

PHI 140780

PHI 316307

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0466 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 242

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5699

Kaibel, G. 1878. *Epigrammata graeca ex lapidibus conlecta.* Berolini. At no.718

Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. *Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes.* Paris. At 510

Manganaro, G. 1994. *Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 95 no.8

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1290. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353373>